

An overview on Semi-solid casting: Observations, Application

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Abstract

The objective of this study was to find out some specific key findings for the processing effects on the semi-solid slurry and its impact on the cast properties of the aluminum based alloys. In this focused review article, effect of semi-solid slurry on the cast composite has been discussed according to processing parameters, technological aspects and its applications.

Keywords: Semi-solid Slurry, Casting, Temperature, Processing

1.1 Introduction

The aluminum industries are of recent time has ultimate goal of single-step manufacturing for the components with various shapes, sound structural integrity, and properties comparable to the wrought state at a low cost. Among these, progressive development and innovations of technology along with factors like design, cost, productivity, speed to market with respect to quality is in progress. Commercialization of the developed technology is a prime factor for any nation and sector to retain their existence in this global economy. On these technologies, one such technology, which has reached to all metal industries, is processing of metals in semi-solid stage e.g. semi-solid casting, semi-solid forming etc. It is believed that the emerging technology of semi-solid processing may satisfy the requirements of these industries. Although, semi-solid processing is already established as a viable method of manufacturing, and currently under intensive development but a critical breakthrough is still expected.

In recent days, importance for semi-solid casting has been well accepted among various processing routes for aluminum alloys, and this is a main consideration for the present thesis. Further, this process has been emerged as an advanced metal processing route for the composites and components by the use of consolidated stirring and squeeze actions. Here, process utilizes scrap aluminum micro size chips and nano size fine powder as reinforcement for similar aluminum base alloys. The process is a simple way to reduce porosity of the cast composite by the advantage of un-melted chips inside the cavities with increased density. The key of semi-solid process is dendrite free slurry with the solid being present as non-agglomerated, fine and spherical particles formation for improved mechanical properties [1-21].

The present chapter provides an overview in brief of the technological and processing aspects of the semi-solid casting. A glimpse of the current status is presented, which shows the potential of the process which can be utilized by the industries for several benefits. Finally, the chapter also describes the organization of present research work and this is well expected that the present chapter will be very useful to understand and evaluate the fundamental and various applications of the semi-solid casting better.

1.2 SEMI-SOLID METAL PROCESSING: AN OVERVIEW

Semi-solid casting is considered to be one of the most important and effective manufacturing processes of aluminum alloy for viable mechanical and metallurgical properties in the current perspective of product requirement and competitiveness. Semi-solid Metal (SSM) stage is also known as 'Mushy State' [3,4]. The following points are generally considered for SSM Casting:

- Heating just above to solidus line (liquid metal appears), state is called Mushy State
- A molten metal is cooled down to a temperature lower than its liquidus line (Solid grains appears), state is called Semi-solid State [3,4]
- Semi-solid stage depends on the amount of regenerated solid grain particles inside the melt. In this stage, slurry becomes thick (low viscous) when high solidified grains appear as shown in figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1 Solid fraction inside the molten metal [4]

Semi-solid state is generated by the partial solidification of the metal in which solid fraction increases to a range of 60% to 95% and metal deforms like a lump of clay. If solid fraction is less than 60% then metal flow like slurry under the gravity force.

Figure 1.2 Representation of viscosity changes with respect to fraction of solid at different level of Dendrite Coherency Point (DCP) [5]

SSM processing deals with the Semi-solid slurries, and results in non-dendritic solid particles are dispersed in a liquid matrix. Moreover, SSM processing have been developed based on unique rheological properties due to non-dendritic microstructures. Solid fraction affects the viscosity of the slurry and α -Al dendrites in case of

Al-Si alloys as described in figure 1.2. Liquid-like SSM slurry is considered as a suspension in which interacting solid particles of low cohesion are dispersed in a liquid matrix. Semisolid metal slurries with a solid fraction less than 0.6 with globular solid particles usually depict two unique rheological properties such as:

- Thixotropy
- Pseudoplasticity

In semi-solid stage below the liquidus line (about 0.7 times of melting temperature) α -Al grains increases [5, 6]. In Semi-solid Casting SSM slurries are performed in three different modes:

- Continuous cooling and shearing from a temperature above the liquids line
- Transient or steady state experiments from a specified starting condition under fixed solid fraction.
- Shearing after partial solidification or partial re-melting.

In above all stages microstructure are affected by present solid particles inside the melt. The key of semi-solid process is dendrite free slurry with the solid being present as non-agglomerated, fine and spherical particles formation for improved mechanical properties. The work carried out and reported by several researchers for low superheat casting with and without superheat suggests that it is possible to thixoform the metal feedstock into a simple part after being held at 580° C [3-5]. Recently many researchers suggested that thixoforming has various advantages over hot conventional casting and forming through the stirring process for aluminum alloy and analyzed the behavior of metallurgical phase change of α -Al alloy during solidification of molten metal at temperature range of 580°C which is approx 2/3rd of the melting temperature [1-6]. Further, melt stirred and mixed with other materials such as ceramic particles, ceramic fibers, graphite fibers and more reinforcement particles which results in improve and fine microstructure with excellent properties. Furthermore, melt is stirred and cooled simultaneously; the solid grains are separated by the stirring force and fix their shapes independently without connecting with other present particles. In semi-solid stage, high cooling rate leads towards the increase in the formation of solid grains inside the melt [1-7]. Whereas, low cooling rate results in small grain formation affected by pouring temperature, stirring and other processing parameters. In the process, during processing, mutual penetration of the liquid components and the solidification as one body, the joining between the components is accomplished to form thick slurry. This formation of slurry effectively depends on

the simultaneous effect of cooling rate and influences the viscosity of the melt. Nonetheless, several reports show that a combined effect of speed and time provides uniform distribution and grain growth of the cast.

Solidification can adversely affects the cast properties with homogeneous solidification which is an essential requirement. In the semi-solid casting, more the injection specific pressure, higher the ability of the slurry to fill the mould cavity to provide the compact casting with highly consistent shape, size and a number of grains. The inclusion of solid metal particles/chips to create partially solid slurry as opposed to control cooling for create solid-liquid slurry had not done in conventional thixocasting/Compo-casting. The higher cooling rate produces better primary refinement of secondary elements, which minimizes its variation with melt temperature [6]. In aluminum industries, parts and components for applications in automobile, aerospace, and construction fields have been fabricated by the die casting, pressurized casting and other immerging techniques including semi-solid processing. The process is very cost effective and leads towards the utilization of scraps.

1.3 TECHNOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF SEMI-SOLID CASTING

Semi-solid processing is modern technology, in which the solid-state techniques generally require multi-step operations after conventional casting, such as homogenization of chemistry, hot working, cold working, forming, machining, or heat treatment. As a result, the properties of wrought components are predominantly superior to castings. Further, the number of manufacturing steps and their complexity, however, contribute to a significantly higher cost of the final product. The economy factor represents the downside of many non-conventional manufacturing techniques. Thus, there is a continuous question for a technology that would reduce costs and at the same time improve properties.

In the past decade, semi-solid casting metal processing route has experienced more vital improved research and development. Now these days, Semi-solid/ Mushy metal casting has been established itself as a huge demanding and viable technique to fabricate metallic components of complex shapes with excellent mechanical properties. The process has tight dimensional control with high integrity with respect to conventional casting process. Further, it is an important aspect of the process is that, the process demonstrated an extensive potential for further development and huge scope in commercial exploitations [1-8].

Figure 1.3 shows a description of thixoforming process. In the process, partially melted metal (non dendritic) filled in a die for the required net shape. The process is employed in two type of die for two different prospects as:

- If the shaping process is achieved in open die under high impact force then the process is called as Thixoforging. [6]
- If the shaping process is achieved in close die high gradual force then the process is called as Thixocasting. [6]

Figure 1.3 Schematic illustration of Thixoforming process [6]

In thixoforming processes, two distinct temperature dependent stages are involved generally. These stages are influences the phase condition of the processed metal. Initially, in first or primary stage metal is partially re-melted by the uniform heating. Further in second stage, semi-solid slug is converted to the final shape product [6]. This process is quite different in semi-solid casting, in which melt is converted to semi-solid slug (in form of slurry) in first stage and then poured into the mould cavity to get net shape of the product in second stage [8]. In the process, some time need a short force application to the slurry which is generally depends on the viscosity of the slurry. The process is shown schematically in figure 1.4. In semi-solid casting/rheocasting process a direct transformation of slurry into a net finished shape. Although the process is identified as a premium technology in early stage (in 1970) but it has not effectively commercialized so far without a great extent. In the process, mechanically stirring actions are included by the stirrer (rod or impeller), which results in formation of short bubbles which further busted suddenly. These bubbles form jet in the

direction parallel to the base inside the melt. Further, these actions result in the formation of very fine rosettes a diameter of few hundred micrometers as well as some time in millimeters.

Figure 1.4 Schematic illustration of Thixocasting process [6]

However, production of components directly from the semi-solid metal slurries is very attractive for aluminum industries due to its important characteristics as follows:

- Integration of slurry making and component shaping operation into one single step process.
- The slurry making operation is quite efficient.
- The process is capable of providing a microstructure comprising fine and spherical particles distributed uniformly in a liquid matrix.
- Efficient and accurate process control.
- Flexibility for the use of several type of reinforcement in the primary melt

The simplicity of the process with technological advantages has led to excellent realization by most casting industries.

1.4 INDUSTRIAL APPLICATIONS

An industrial interest was developed after a research initiated at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology in the early 1970s, by Spencer and teammate [9]. During this process, stirring of alloys at the time of solidification led to a remarkable change in the cast microstructure resulting not only in a significant reduction in apparent viscosity of the slurry in semi-solid stage with a facility of flow for two-phase homogeneous metal at high rate of solid fraction. By, early 1990s the MIT research had explored a concept for the use of semi-solid material as a feedstock for die-cast components in horizontally flow. After this successful experimentation, SSM casting processes recognized and adopted among other conventional processes in which improved capability of the process was found to producing high quality parts [10, 11].

The process was adopted for commercial applications of the new modified technology for aluminum alloy parts were in fact as well as for copper alloys, which was direct implemented to closed die in semi-solid stage. Effectiveness of the process was found in which 100% of the charge material was finally converted to finished part [12].

For mass production of thin section components, high pressure die casting are conventionally selected due to excellent level of process success [6, 8, 12]. Semi-solid metals in the form of slurry for castings not delivered only excellent mechanical properties, but also very refine microstructure and potential to alteration of mixing of several types of reinforcements. Components made by die casting process always contains some small level of porosity, but it may be minimize by the use of very short stroke time and pouring temperature. Further, this porosity has potential to variability in properties, which makes component durable and non-heat treatable.

Figure 1.5 Impact of SQC process over conventional processes [15]

Table 1.1 Rating with respect to squeeze casting [15]

Factors↓	Gravity Casting	Die Casting	Forging	SQC
Economy	C	A	D	B
Reliability	C	D	A	B
Design Flexibility	A	C	D	B
Complexity	C	A	D	B
A for Superior		D for Inferior		

For thick section components, especially in automobile components like chassis and suspension parts Squeeze casting (SQC) is very well adopted due to higher density components [2, 6, 13-15]. In the process, pressurized solidification process has been conducted excellently. Importance of process is summarized in figure 1.5 and table 1.1.

Table 1.2 Potential automotive applications for various processes [15]

Components applicable for Squeeze Casting	
A	Piston, Cylinder, Gear box, Wheel
B	Brake drum, Clutch Housing, Engine Block
C	Connecting rod , Suspension arm, Piston

Rating for the products fabricated by the various processes are compared with some factors is summarized in table 1.1. [15]. This process has capability to produce high strength, heat treatable, strength and ductile components similar to SSM casting, but effectively not suitable for the thin section components [6, 15, 16]. Thus, both the processes are consolidated to achieve the process capability for thin section components. From table 1.1, it is very clear that Squeeze casting process is not superior and nor inferior. Further, SQC process is employed for thin sections are listed for various applications in table 1.2.

Table 1.3 Comparison of cost elements and relative bottom line components

Cost	SSM forming	Die casting	Squeeze Casting	PMC
Material	2.5	1	1.25	1.25
Tooling	1	2	3	1.5
Capital	1.2	1	1.2	1
Labor	1.2	1.1	1.3	1
Heat Treating	1	NA	3	3
Machining	1	1	1.2	2
Finishing	1	1.5	1	2
Bottom Line Casting	2	1	2.2	3

Here 1 represents lowest cost

Permanent mould casting (PMC) process is also good for high integrity components but only for thin sections. This process is generally used for aluminum alloy wheels and structural components. In above all, compared overall production cost for the components are summarized in table 1.3.

1.5 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE WORK

- A lot of experimental works have been performed by the use of micro coarse ceramics. This work also has potential with the use of fine ceramics along with micro chip particles.
- The work can be suggested for the increase properties of the cast billets/ ingots used for the secondary processes for fabrication of components.
- The work can be perform for the MAGNALIUM alloys (Magnalium is an aluminum alloy with magnesium and small amounts of nickel and tin, used in aircraft and automobile parts)
- A good scope is available for the consolidated effect of Microwave Heating at low and self pouring temperature with powder-chip reinforcement for excellent level of properties of the cast composite.

Conclusions

After extensive review the following key observations have been drawn:

- Cast components are in need of scientific understandings and technological development. The several attempts have been made to improve the properties for more efficient products by the use of Semi-solid Metal processing due to capability of fine microstructure.
- Most of the studies are for the improvement of particular application focusing towards automobile component and aluminum industries. Semi-solid processing might be useful for these integrated components with improved strength.
- By the use of Semi-solid Metal (SSM) casting, the energy requirement (for melting) and material savings (effective utilization of scrap) with reduction in wastage can be achieved.
- Semisolid casting have potential of fabrication in a temperature range below the melting point of a metal, influenced by the incomplete recrystallization, low turbulence of the melt which causes formation of globular structure.
- Preparation of semisolid slurry is possible by mixing several type of reinforcement with refined microstructure due to uniform distribution of reinforcement particles on the surfaces.

- Components made by SSM have functionality for the combination of forming and joining in one single step with the adjustment of alloys to specific demands with excellent level of mechanical properties.

In a nutshell it can be found that process have capability of alteration by the use of different scraps and also have flexibility according to the processing parameters like stirring, pouring temperature, type of reinforcements etc.

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